

OBJECTIVE AND SUBJECTIVE FACTORS OF THE SPIRITUAL-MORAL TRAGEDY OF IMAGES IN CHINGIZ AYTMATOV'S WORKS

Abdugapparova Shodiyona Adashali qizi

ToshDO'TAU, PhD student

Shodiyona1993@inbox.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13861622>

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada Chingiz Aytmatovning "Qiyomat" romanidagi bir qator obrazlarning ma'naviy-axloqiy olamidagi evrilishlar qiyosiy jihatdan tahlilga tortilgan. O'z navbatida obrazlar ma'naviy-axloqiy fojiasining obyektiv va subyektiv omillari tadqiq qilingan.

Annotation

In this article, evolutions in the spiritual and moral world of a number of characters in Chingiz Aitmatov's novel "Doomsday" are analyzed from a comparative point of view. In turn, the objective and subjective factors of the spiritual and moral tragedy of images were studied.

Аннотация

В данной статье со сравнительной точки зрения анализируется эволюция духовно-нравственного мира ряда персонажей романа Чингиза Айтматова «Судный день». В свою очередь, изучались объективные и субъективные факторы духовно-нравственной трагедии образов.

Kalit so'zlar

Obraz, fojia, ma'naviy-axloqiy olam, roman, subyektiv omil, obyektiv omil, Grishan, Avdiy, Ober-Kandalov, Bo'ston, Bozorboy.

Keywords

Image, tragedy, spiritual and moral world, novel, subjective factor, objective factor, Grishan, Avdiy, Ober-Kandalov, Boston, Bozorboy.

Ключевые слова

Образ, трагедия, духовно-нравственный мир, роман, субъективный фактор, объективный фактор, Гришан, Авдий, Обер-Кандалов, Бостон, Бозорбой.

In the works of Chingiz Aitmatov, the principle of a person being worthy of the name human is considered the highest goal. In the stages of artistic improvement of his work, the writer moves from stories to short stories, from short stories to novels, and lives with this principle, this goal, this idea in each of his works. In the last work of the writer, the novel "Qiyamat", this idea is embodied in a particularly lively and deep way. The spiritual-spiritual world, moral-ethical state, and tragedy of a person are described through a deep philosophical observation. Philosophical ideas in the novel are aimed at arousing an active inner attitude in the reader, mobilizing him spiritually, protecting true human values despite any external reasons. The attitude of the heroes of the novel to life, nature, thoughts, philosophical views, similar destinies, harmony with time - all this cannot but excite the reader. The work is a basis for thinking about the essence of existence, the uncompromising struggle against immorality, which is alien to our lives and causes incalculable damage to the natural development of man. Objective and subjective factors that cause the spiritual and moral growth or tragedy of a person are severely criticized in the novel. The writer clearly shows to the reader that the dehumanization of a person is not only his character or himself, but that his surroundings,

relatives, social status, and the whole society are also to blame, in the example of each hero, each image, and their tragedies. could show. The writer puts forward certain shortcomings of the society in which he lives, a number of problems that cause people's lives to be ruined, which calls on every person and every society to be aware. The writer's exclamation points to the unity of man-society-nature, which means that disaster is inevitable if it is not united. In the work, the development of events converges around several ideas. He touches deeply on the problem of drug addiction, which is becoming a social disease among today's youth, and calls on the public to fight against it. The philosophical meaning of the novel indicates the possibility of wide interpretation, each image and detail is symbolic and contains not one, but many meanings. The novel has several plot and composition directions: Avdiy Kallistratov, personal fate of Boston Urkunchayev; junta crowd, drug addicts; The fate of the wolf family is a seemingly independent part of the work. However, despite this, they are connected to each other, closely related to each other by the totality of the problems, and form a certain unity.

The moral and moral tragedy of several heroes is evident in the work. First, one of the plot lines of the multi-planned work is the spiritual and moral tragedy of drug addiction and the criminals involved in its trade, which is one of today's pressing problems. When Avdiy entered this group, "if I turn these people away from the bad path, if I open their eyes, they will look at themselves with a different, open perspective, and get rid of the fear that poisons their lives and the persecution of this fear.", he dreams ¹. " He tries to turn the gang of criminals away. While arguing with Avdiy, one of the leaders of this group, Grishan said, "I bring joy to people. They reach God's presence in joy. What I give, they will not find in your exhortations, sermons, prayers and prayers... I will lead my people to God faster than anyone else... That's it! Don't do it! Everything in the world is sold and bought, including your God. But I say people should enjoy it. I will fulfill in this world what you have promised in words and what is more in the next world. Being alone gives you pleasure, you feel free in the world like a bird, you fly to the sky. Well, let this pleasure, this pleasure, pass in the blink of an eye. Well, let it happen. But there is happiness in it, happiness in it, and it can only be achieved unconsciously . And you, the pious, are deprived of even this dream ².

Another spiritual and moral tragedy in the play finds its artistic expression through a gang of detectives. Ober Kandalov: "You can't scare us with God. The people you think are different, kanji! Who are you? We are fulfilling the state's mission here, you, Kanjik, are against the plan, against the region. It turns out that you, dirty, are an enemy of the people, an enemy of the people and the state. There is no place on earth for enemies, pests, subversives like you! Hey church rat, do you know what you're doing? You want to ruin everything! You're messing up the assignment! You want to turn all of our faces to the ground. Hey, I'll strangle you like a public enemy. They thank me. Because you are a spy of imperialism, dirty! You say that there is no Stalin, we will do what we want, right? You pop's gazanda, come on, kneel down, kneel down now. Behold, I am your ruler. Back from God! I don't know, I don't know! Give up! On the contrary, you go to Asfalasofilin, dirty!

- Talk, filthy, roared Ober-Kandalov - turn away from God! Say! Say there is no God!³

¹ Chingiz Aytmatov, "Asrga tatigulik kun". – T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2005. 122-bet.

² Chingiz Aytmatov, "Asrga tatigulik kun". – T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2005. 167-bet.

³ Chingiz Aytmatov, "Asrga tatigulik kun". – T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2005. 281-bet.

From the plot lines of the play, in the uncompromising fight between Bo'ston and Bozorboy, the spiritual and moral tragedy of Bozorboy shows its height: "Where are you in a hurry, dog? Bazarboy stood up, bent down, and brought his angry face closer to Boston. Where are you in a hurry, you fool? We haven't talked about wolves with you yet. After all, you provoked me in the middle of everyone at the meeting in the director's office, because of me wolves are strangling the rabid sheep. You don't think I know what the challenger means? Do you think I'm bad, but you are the only conscientious and honest among us?"⁴

In conclusion, Academician B. Nazarov asked whether "Chingiz Aitmatov, setting free his artistic imagination in the work, describes the slaughter of saigas, which is being carried out by wild over-Kandalovites in the deserts of Moyinqum in our time, Bo around Issqikol whether it reflects the life of the shepherds of the working livestock farm, whether it takes the events to the drug fields around the "Uchkuduq" state farm, - it focuses on the problem of faith as the main feature that defines the identity of the characters involved in all of them ⁵. These images cause not only their lives but also the lives of other people in the society to be destroyed due to the weakness of faith in them. The problem of faith is considered an objective factor of the spiritual and moral tragedy of the heroes of the work. But although it is not explicitly stated in the novel, the main causes of these heroes' lives are not themselves, but the people around them, the society that surrounds them, the upper class that forces them to fall into this situation are not the main causes of their moral and spiritual tragedy. factors such as the state's representatives, the tyranny of the state, which is indifferent to the spiritual tragedy, and the humiliation of human dignity, show their importance as a subjective factor in the tragedy of these heroes.

References:

1. Chingiz Aytmatov, "Asrga tatigulik kun". – T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2005. 122-bet.
2. O'zbek adabiyoti. 11-sinf uchun darslik. – T.: "O'qituvchi", 1995-yil, 347-349-betlar.
3. A.Rashidov. Chingiz Aytmatov olami. -T.: "O'qituvchi" NMIU. 2011 - 256 b.

⁴ Chingiz Aytmatov, "Asrga tatigulik kun". – T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2005. 402-bet.

⁵ O'zbek adabiyoti. 11-sinf uchun darslik. – T.: "O'qituvchi", 1995-yil, 347-349-betlar.